

Appendix I – Comprehensibility Guidelines Applied in This Study

This list is not exhaustive but considers several literature reviews, such as Avila et al. (2021), Corradini et al. (2018) and Oca et al. (2015), making the guidelines listed here representative of the main recommended practices.

GUIDELINES	SUGGESTED ACTIONS	REFERENCE
Syntactic Rules	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Activities must have at least one incoming and one outgoing sequence flow. 2. Sequence flows must connect two elements within the same pool (they cannot connect elements between two different pools). 3. Message flows must connect an activity or event from one pool to another (never within the same pool). 4. All elements must have a path from the start event to the end event. 	Dumas et al., 2018.
Validation (Semantic Quality)	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Individual interviews or workshops may be conducted to ensure that the model faithfully represents the main parts of the process. 	Dumas et al., 2018.
Model Size	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Eliminate unnecessary or duplicate elements in the model. 2. Remove or merge activities that are excessively detailed and have a low level of granularity. 3. Split models with more than 31 elements into smaller parts or use subprocesses. 4. Simplify readability using subprocesses. 5. Group repeated process fragments into a call activity. 6. Redistribute activities between subprocesses and the higher-level process. 7. Avoid using more than seven events per model. 8. Avoid unnecessary or duplicate intermediate events by removing or redistributing them across subprocesses. 9. Minimize the number of incoming and outgoing flows per gateway. 10. Maintain the shortest possible path between start and end elements. 11. When decisions are related, combine multiple gateways. 12. Check whether consecutive activities in a lane can be unified or grouped. 13. Process details may be described in supplementary documentation. 	Mendling et al., 2010; Corradini et al., 2018; Oca & Snoeck, 2014; Kahloun & Ghannouchi, 2018; Avila et al., 2021.
Gateways	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Each activity or event must have only one incoming and one outgoing sequence flow. 2. Use the exclusive (XOR) gateway with the “X” marker. 3. Splitting gateways must have one incoming and at least two outgoing flows. 4. Joining gateways must have at least two incoming and one outgoing flow. 5. Avoid more than 12 gateways per model. 6. The number of gateways can be reduced by using subprocesses. 7. Avoid more than three routes per gateway whenever possible. 8. Use one gateway to split paths and another to merge them. 	Leopold et al., 2016; Mendling et al., 2010; Corradini et al., 2018; Oca & Snoeck, 2014; Avila et al., 2021.

Parallel Gateways	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Limit the number of outgoing paths per gateway to a maximum of eight. 2. Ensure that all parallel paths lead to end events and are synchronized. 	Oca & Snoeck, 2014.
Inclusive OR Gateways	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Whenever possible, replace them with simpler options such as XOR or parallel gateways. 2. If their use is necessary to represent process complexity, use a gateway of the same type to merge the paths. 	Mendling et al., 2010; Corradini et al., 2018; Oca & Snoeck, 2014.
Events	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Start events must not have incoming flows. 2. End events must not have outgoing flows. 3. Intermediate events must have at least one incoming and one outgoing flow. 4. Only intermediate events may be used as boundary events. 5. Use only one start event; if multiple situations can initiate the process, represent them using a gateway. 6. Distinguish success and failure end states. 7. End events that do not represent distinct final states should be merged into a single end event. 8. Terminal events should be used only in strict cases. 	Mendling et al., 2010; Corradini et al., 2018; Oca & Snoeck, 2014; Kahloun & Ghannouchi, 2018.
Structured Models	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Each splitting gateway must have a corresponding gateway of the same type. 2. Avoid implicit splits and joins when building models. 	Mendling et al., 2010; Corradini et al., 2018; Oca & Snoeck, 2014.
Loops	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Avoid unnecessary loops in the model. 2. Reduce the number of loops exits, if possible. 3. Prefer using elements with loop markers, such as activities or subprocesses, to simplify the model. 4. Use exclusive (XOR) gateways to start and end a loop. 5. Avoid using distinct types of gateways simultaneously to ensure clarity and simplicity. 6. Attach a text annotation to the looping activity or subprocess. 	Corradini et al., 2018; Oca & Snoeck, 2014.
Messages	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. All sending/receiving activities and events must have an associated message flow. 2. Use subprocesses to reduce the number of message flows. 3. If there are multiple message flows to the same pool in subprocesses, display only one outgoing and one incoming flow in the higher-level process. 	Corradini et al., 2018; Kahloun & Ghannouchi, 2018.
Labels	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Use “verb + object” to name activities. 2. The verb must always be in infinitive form and familiar to the team. 3. Do not include the element type in the label (e.g., activity, event etc.). 4. Avoid using identical labels for different activities, except for call activities. 5. Reserve “Send” and “Receive” verbs for specific sending/receiving activities. 6. Label all events in the model. 7. For timer events, include date/time parameters whenever possible. 8. Label link events with a noun. 9. Conditional events should be labeled according to the triggering condition. 10. To ensure clarity, exclusive (XOR) split gateways should be labeled with a question (while join XOR gateways should not be labeled). 11. Outgoing sequence flows from divergent gateways should be labeled with the corresponding condition (e.g., “Yes/No”). 12. Do not label parallel (AND) splits/joins or their related flows. 	Mendling et al., 2010; Corradini et al., 2018; Oca & Snoeck, 2014.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 13. Label pools with the process name. 14. Label black box pools with the participant's name. 15. Label lanes with the names of internal agents (departments, systems, people etc.). 	
Pools and Lanes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Use one pool for each process and external participant involved. 2. For external participants, use black box pools. 3. Internal organizational units must be modeled as lanes within a single pool rather than as separate pools. 4. Lanes should only be used if they contain an activity or intermediate event. 5. Avoid using lanes to represent participants who perform only automated tasks or contain only gateways. 	<p>Corradini et al., 2018; Oca & Snoeck, 2014; Kahloun & Ghannouchi, 2018.</p>
Subprocesses	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Use subprocesses when: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) A set of consecutive activities has a different owner than the main process. b) A set of consecutive activities has a different goal than the main process. c) A process or part of it must be reused in another process (call activities). 2. To better represent the scope of an event. 3. Activities that can be performed by the same person may be grouped into a subprocess or a single activity. 4. The labels of subprocess end states must be synchronized with the label of the gateway immediately following the subprocess. 	<p>Corradini et al., 2018; Oca & Snoeck, 2014; Kahloun & Ghannouchi, 2018.</p>
Layout	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Draw connectors orthogonally, using right angles. 2. Draw pools horizontally. 3. Build long, narrow models, avoiding square-shaped diagrams. 4. Connect objects following the workflow direction. 5. Minimize drawing area. 6. Use a consistent flow layout style. 7. Avoid overlapping elements and crossing lines. 8. Use straight, linear sequence flows without unnecessary bends. 9. Use a horizontal layout for sequence flows and a vertical one for message flows and associations. 10. Place elements symmetrically and position related elements close to each other. 	<p>Corradini et al., 2018; Oca & Snoeck, 2014.</p>

Source: prepared by authors.